

The Alan Turing Institute

Contextualising Research Projects and Collaboration

Malvika Sharan, Georgia Aitkenhead
Pronouns: she/her/hers

Context

Latin of **to knit together**, **to make a connection** or **to link**

Context in Research

Latin of to knit together, to make a connection or to link

Linking research to the context of research setting, background and the future impact.

Context in Research

[Research] is highly situational, contingent and dependent on the privilege and context of knowledge makers, receivers and gatekeepers.

Contextualising Openness, 2020, edited by Leslie Chan, A. Okune, R. Hillyar, D. Albornoz, A. Posada

Contextualisation in Research

Considering the influence of
(*social, cultural, historical,*
political, educational, technical...)
contexts **where knowledge is
produced** in relation to **where it is
received and used.**

Rousseau, D. M., & Fried, Y. (2001). Location, location, location: contextualizing organizational research*. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 22(1), 1–13. doi: 10.1002/job.78,

Image by Scriberia for The Turing Way, Shared under CC-BY 4.0, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5724333

Research as a Process

Figure 1. Framework: Contextual Constructs Model (adapted from Knight, 2008)

Contextualising Locally

- Research Setting
- Stakeholders
- Skills & knowledge gaps
- Tools, practices, resources
- Present timing
- Configuration

Contextualising Widely

- Prior studies (history)
- Other disciplines
- Other locations
- Future impact
- Benefits and harms
- Who/what is missing?

Rousseau, D. M., & Fried, Y. (2001). Location, location, location: contextualizing organizational research*. *Journal of Organizational Behavior*, 22(1), 1–13. doi: 10.1002/job.78,

Image by Scriberia for The Turing Way, Shared under CC-BY 4.0, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5724333

A tool for Democratising Knowledge

Contextualisation in research **enhances participation** of diverse stakeholders, **collaboration** among developers and users, and **enable access** to research objects/process.

Rethinking Knowledge Production & Circulation

Access is not only about being able to read but being able to have a voice and shape the direction of disciplines, economic models and infrastructure.

- Juan Pablo Alperin

References: Mewa, & Goudarzi. (2018). Mapping Academic Publishing: Locating Enclaves of Development Knowledge. EElectronic PUBLISHing, Connecting the Knowledge Commons: From Projects to Sustainable Infrastructure, Image: <https://doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.953177>, Quote: <https://www.force11.org/blog/open-access-inclusion-interview-juan-pablo-alperin>

Are Stakeholders Impacted by the Research outcome?

Involving “local actors” in addressing issues and decision-making process that impact them.

Contexts and activities that are more likely to reflect local realities, as opposed to replicating western constructs or institutionalized forms of research.

AutSPACEs

The
Alan Turing
Institute

Research by and for autistic people

The
Alan Turing
Institute

AutSPACEs

- Collaboration between *The Alan Turing Institute* and *Autistica*
- To build an online citizen science platform
- Investigating how sensory processing differences affect how autistic people navigate the world
- Using participatory co-design throughout

Research by and for autistic people

Contextualising Autism Research

Society tends to disempower autistic people:

- just **22%** in paid work
- **75%** live with parents
- **9x** higher suicide rate
- **27%** of children with autism have been excluded from school
- Women and girls diagnosed on average later than men and boys

Autism research can be disempowering:

- Often framed as “dysfunction” or “disease”
- History of looking for causes and *prevention* still impacting research and perceptions of research
- Priorities do not match funding
- Movement towards autism advocacy and call for change

Historicising Autism Research: changing narratives

- "Little Professor"
- Autistic spectrum
- Autistic Constellation Model

<https://www.autangel.org.uk/resources/#constellationmodel>

Research impacts include:

- Self-understanding
- Interpersonal dynamics
- Societal perceptions
- Societal discrimination or acceptance
- Access to support and services
- Access to institutions of knowledge
- how research is done

Self-perpetuating cycle

“...make it easier for people to, I wouldn't say function, I would say live...bring their talents out, uncover their potential”

Autistic parent to an autistic person

More than consulting

- Priority setting
- Decision making
- Co-authorship
- Co-presenting
- Co-designing
- Community growth

#CogX2020

gaitkenhead@turing.ac.uk

10.5281/zenodo.3886558

“I’m autistic so I’ve got an awful lot of experience which I hope to contribute to the group” *Autistic adult*

Mapping the project

Design

Strategy

Legal

Advice

Comms

Code

Ideas Networks

Who is in danger of being left out?

- Autistic people with learning differences
- Non-verbal autistic people
- Black autistic people (harder to be diagnosed)
- Socially anxious or isolated people
- Carers with full time responsibilities
- Non-English speakers
- UK-based, so not global

Our Community

- Dev Volunteers
- Autistic volunteers
- Turing/lab members
- Open Life Sciences
- The Turing Way
- Open Humans
- GSoC
- UK Civil Service

The Alan Turing Institute

Supporting our community

- Meet-up sessions
- Twitter
- GitHub support
- One to one working
- Co-working
- Supporting diversity
- Creating inclusive spaces

The bigger picture: open

Working openly means code for a platform which can be **easily adapted** for other research projects and research method and resources which **can be reused**.

Increased scope, wider context

Contextualising Research

Configuration and roles of structural power in your contexts:

- To whom does knowledge **belong**?
- Who **benefits from the production and circulation** of knowledge?
- Who gets to **participate**?
- In what ways can technology be used to **increase the agency** of more people over knowledge?

Contextualising Research

Configuration and roles of structural power in your contexts:

- To whom does knowledge belong?
- Who benefits from the production and circulation of knowledge?
- Who gets to participate?
- In what ways can technology be used to increase the agency of more people over knowledge?

Figure 2.1. OCSDNet Manifesto Infographic

Contextualising Research Projects

Facilitating Responsible Participation Special Interest Group,
The Alan Turing Institute, UK.

Contextualisation in research is a way to consider the influence of historical, social, cultural and technical contexts where knowledge is produced in relation to where it is received and used. This worksheet is designed to reflect on participation, access and facilitating collaboration in research projects.

Choose a research project that you are working on and get started with this worksheet! Compare your worksheets with other colleagues in the project.

Project Details:

Project title, affiliation, important links and stakeholders/actors (developers, collaborators, contributors, funders, users etc.) details.

Title:

Affiliation:

Links:

Stakeholders:

Social, Cultural & Historical Context

in which this project takes place:

Add text here

in which knowledge produced from this project is received:

Add text here

Goals	Short-term goals	Long-term goals
Project goals	Add text here	Add text here
Sustainable goals (social, global)		

Different Forms of Participation

Ensuring participation of all actors in research and resource management through project design, implementation and uptake processes.

Equitable collaboration and communication

Ensuring effective collaboration and communication process to avoid possible exclusion of all stakeholders including informal and local groups. Details on how you will seek support and in what ways you might be able to help/support others.

Overlapping Interests	Researchers in the Project	Social actors affected by the project
Skills & lived experience	Add text here	Add text here
Positive impact		
Negative impact		

Tools, Resources & Inclusive Infrastructure

Promoting interactions between data providers and data users, and enable them to produce, gather, share, collaborate, and use scientific knowledge.

TIPS: Contextualisation in research covers some of the following aspects

Project Design

- Question/hypothesis formulation
- Design and methodology
- Data collection and wrangling
- Data analysis and reporting
- Interpretation/discussion of findings
- Implications and conclusions
- Sharing and archiving

Inclusive Collaboration

- Communication platforms
- Documentation & guidance
- roles and responsibilities
- process and standards
- development plans & workflow
- training, supervision & support
- sharing, publication & archiving
- opportunities to celebrate!

Planning Research Collaboration

The Turing Way Workshop

In *The Turing Way*, we consider collaboration essential for reproducible research and provide a separate guide with best practices and recommendations for your reference.

Choose one research project that you are currently working on and get started with this worksheet!

Communication within the project

Preferred channels and tools, Communication norms and policies (links to documents).

GitHub, Slack, email, newsletters, HackMD for shared documents, google drive share slides, Twitter, community events, Code of Conduct, online protocols, data management, co-created resources for understanding and reviewing data, Zoom, Netlify page

Project Details:

Project title, affiliation, important links and stakeholders details.

Title: AutSPACES

Affiliation: The Alan Turing Institute, Autistica

Links: GitHub (project management):

<https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/AutisticaCitizenScience>

GitHub (platform development):

<https://github.com/alan-turing-institute/AutSPACES>

Stakeholders: Core research team, autistic collaborators, funders, organisational partners (Open Humans, Fujitsu), open source community,

Ways to Collaborate

List all opportunities for knowledge exchange such as events, meetings, 1:1 feedback, project management and task allocation processes etc.

Co-working calls with the AutSPACES community (2 hr) every 2nd and 4th Thursday, weekly development sessions (2hr) with open source contributors and researchers, GitHub for facilitating all kinds of contributions and discussions, project slack channel review, newsletters to share monthly updates, focus groups, co-design sessions and discussion sessions with autistic people and their relatives/supporters, tailored collaboration for those who need it, email

Skills

Learn in this project:

Community management and development, scoping and funding, tech skills: Django and Python, autism (lived experience)

Teach others in this project:

Open collaboration and co-working, neurodiversity, ethics, research protocols, online co-development, autism research

Uncertainties

List what you don't know about the project, what uncertainties in the project exist, how they affect your work, who can you speak about it?

Allocating time and responsibilities for voluntary community

How do we engage more diverse autistic people (such as those with learning differences)

Diversity metrics

How to ensure long-term sustainability

Lots of changes to research team over time: need to maintain consistency

Personal collaboration and development plans

- Keep at least one day a week meeting free for deep work - focus on writing papers
- Gather support in community management and development - work with others to sustain complex workflow without burnout
- Keep momentum and engagement by supporting bi-monthly meetup sessions and ensure continuation even with changing team members
- Use slack for discussion about development and making sure information is exchanged

Goals

Short-term goals

Long-term goals

Shared goals

Deploy an online platform where autistic people can share experiences
Support/ally with autistic people

Collect data which can be used to adapt environments so that they are more enabling for autistic people

Personal goals

Onboard new team members to the AutSPACES project; write two papers on the project, publish dataset on moderation

Make a model repository which can be adapted for other research projects
Build research skills for pursuing PhD/future academic career

Contextualising Research

*By itself, 'research' is just inanimate data: in conversation and contextualised it has the **power to animate, inform, empower or infuriate**. It has the latent capacity to become knowledge, or even evidence.*

Five minutes with Huw Davies: “When contextualised, research has the power to animate, inform, empower or infuriate”. (2017, May 10). Retrieved from <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/impactofsocialsciences/2012/03/23/contextualised-research-policymaking-event>, Image by Scriberia for The Turing Way, Shared under CC-BY 4.0, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5724333

Thank you!

- Malvika Sharan: msharan@turing.ac.uk
- Georgia Aitkenhead: gaitkenhead@turing.ac.uk

Related slides and materials are available under CC-BY 4.0 License: <https://zenodo.org/record/5724333>

Worksheet in PPT format is shared in Google Drive: bit.ly/frp-context-sheet

The
Alan Turing
Institute

